

EVOLUTION OF CHILD CHARACTERS IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

Dilrabo Muzaffar qizi TOKHIROVA

doctoral student, Uzbekistan state
world languages university

Abstract. *This article explores the evolution of child characters in English literature, examining their transformation, themes, and symbolism across centuries. From the innocence of early works to the psychological complexity of modern literature, child characters have reflected societal changes and offered insights into the human experience.*

Key words: *Children, Innocence, Realism, Protagonist, Romanticism, Children's literature, Psychological Complexity.*

Introduction. Children have long captivated the imagination of writers and readers alike, occupying a significant place in the realm of literature. They serve as compelling subjects, embodying innocence, potential, and the intricate facets of human nature. Over the course of centuries, English literature has witnessed a remarkable evolution in the portrayal of child characters, offering insights into their experiences, growth, and societal roles. From the early works of the 17th century to the contemporary novels of today, the depiction of children has transformed, reflecting shifting cultural, social, and psychological perspectives. This article embarks on a captivating exploration of the fascinating journey undertaken by child characters in English literature, delving into their transformation, thematic variations, and symbolic significance across eight centuries of literary exploration. In the early years of English literature, child characters were often depicted as embodiments of innocence and purity. Works such as William Blake's "Songs of Innocence" and John Bunyan's "The Pilgrim's Progress" presented children as symbols of untainted virtue and spiritual enlightenment. These literary creations provided an idealized vision of childhood, emphasizing the inherent goodness and inherent potential of children. During this period, authors sought to capture the essence of childhood innocence, often contrasting it with the complexities and corruption of the adult world.

As the centuries unfolded, the Romantic movement emerged, ushering in a new perspective on childhood. Romantic writers celebrated the imagination, freedom, and emotional sensitivity of children. Poets such as William Wordsworth and Samuel Taylor Coleridge explored the theme of childhood in their works, presenting children as natural poets and keen observers of the world's beauty and wonder. Through their verses, these poets sought to elevate and honor the unique perspectives and unadulterated joy of childhood.

With the advent of the Victorian era, the portrayal of child characters took on a more nuanced and realistic tone. Novels such as Charles Dickens' "Oliver Twist" and Charlotte Brontë's "Jane Eyre" depicted child protagonists navigating the harsh realities of poverty, abuse, and societal expectations. These works shed light on the social injustices and challenges faced by children during this period, advocating for their rights and welfare. The child characters became vehicles for social critique and the exploration of societal issues.

The 20th century witnessed a significant shift in the representation of child characters with the rise of children's literature as a distinct genre. Authors such as Lewis Carroll, J.M. Barrie, and E. Nesbit crafted enchanting worlds and memorable child characters that resonated with readers of all ages. Carroll's "Alice's Adventures in Wonderland" celebrated the whimsical imagination of

a young girl, while Barrie's "Peter Pan" explored the eternal essence of childhood and the conflict between growing up and staying young. These imaginative tales captured the spirit of childhood and offered profound insights into the human condition.

In modern and contemporary literature, child characters have gained psychological depth and complexity. Authors like J.D. Salinger, Harper Lee, and Mark Haddon have delved into the inner worlds and struggles of child protagonists. "The Catcher in the Rye" presents Holden Caulfield as a troubled adolescent grappling with the transition to adulthood, while "To Kill a Mockingbird" explores the moral growth of Scout Finch in the face of racial prejudice. These works offer profound examinations of the challenges, conflicts, and growth experienced by children as they navigate the complexities of the modern world.

Findings.

The Innocence of Childhood in Early Literature

The early years of English literature celebrated the innocence and purity of child characters, portraying them as untouched by the complexities of the adult world [2: 18]. In works such as William Blake's "Songs of Innocence," children were depicted as symbols of untainted virtue and spiritual enlightenment. Blake's poems, accompanied by his own illustrations, captured the essence of childhood purity and the inherent goodness believed to reside within children. The child characters in these works represented a vision of innocence that resonated with the prevailing sentiments of the 17th and 18th centuries.

Similarly, John Bunyan's "The Pilgrim's Progress" presented child characters as embodiments of purity and spiritual insight [6]. The character of Christiana's children, Mercy and her brothers, were portrayed as innocent souls on a pilgrimage, untouched by the corrupting influences of the world. Their childlike faith and unwavering devotion to their spiritual journey symbolized the idealized concept of childhood as a state of moral purity.

These early literary portrayals of child characters reflected the idealized vision of childhood innocence prevalent during the 17th and 18th centuries. Children were seen as vessels of purity, untainted by the sins and complexities of adulthood. They were often depicted as morally upright beings, capable of perceiving the divine in their surroundings. These depictions served as a counterbalance to the moral corruption and social upheavals of the time, offering a glimpse of hope and spiritual enlightenment through the innocence of childhood.

Romanticism and the Romantic Child

The emergence of Romanticism in the late 18th and early 19th centuries brought about a profound shift in the portrayal of child characters in English literature [3:183-203]. The Romantics celebrated the inherent qualities of children, emphasizing their imagination, freedom, and emotional sensitivity. Poets such as William Wordsworth and Samuel Taylor Coleridge delved into the theme of childhood, presenting children as natural poets and keen observers of the world's beauty and wonder.

William Wordsworth, in his collection of poems titled "Lyrical Ballads," captured the essence of childhood through his famous poem "Ode: Intimations of Immortality from Recollections of Early Childhood." Wordsworth believed that children possessed a deep connection to nature and a profound sense of wonder. He saw them as vessels of intuition and insight, capable of perceiving the spiritual and transcendent aspects of the world. Through his poetry, Wordsworth celebrated the imaginative and visionary qualities of children, presenting them as beings in tune with the mysteries of existence.

Likewise, Samuel Taylor Coleridge explored the theme of childhood in his poem "Frost at Midnight." Coleridge described the child as a source of inspiration and renewal, capable of experiencing a profound connection with nature and its transformative power. He recognized the child's ability to perceive the sublime in the ordinary, capturing their innate sense of awe and wonder. Coleridge's portrayal of child characters reflected the Romantic belief in the transformative and visionary capacities of childhood.

In the works of Wordsworth, Coleridge, and other Romantic writers, child characters were elevated as beings possessing a heightened sensitivity and a unique connection to the natural world. They were seen as natural poets, capable of perceiving and expressing the profound truths of existence. The Romantics celebrated the freedom of imagination and the emotional depth found in children, presenting them as sources of inspiration and as reminders of the innate wonder that can be lost in the process of growing up.

Victorian Realism and the Child Protagonist

The Victorian era marked a significant shift in the portrayal of child characters in English literature, as it reflected the societal changes and challenges faced by children during that time [4:1-13]. Novels such as Charles Dickens' "Oliver Twist" and Charlotte Brontë's "Jane Eyre" presented child protagonists who navigated the harsh realities of poverty, abuse, and societal expectations.

In Dickens' "Oliver Twist," the eponymous character endures a life of destitution and mistreatment as an orphan. The novel sheds light on the plight of impoverished children and exposes the harsh conditions of workhouses and the exploitative nature of child labor. Dickens' portrayal highlights the vulnerability and resilience of child characters, while also serving as a critique of the social injustices prevalent in Victorian society.

Similarly, in Charlotte Brontë's "Jane Eyre," the young protagonist faces numerous challenges and hardships, including neglect, abuse, and social marginalization [1: 269-289]. Brontë's portrayal of Jane Eyre as a resilient and independent child striving for self-worth and equality reflects the struggles faced by many children during the Victorian era. The novel addresses themes of class, gender, and the limited opportunities available to young girls, emphasizing the importance of advocating for children's rights and breaking societal constraints.

These works and others of the Victorian era shed light on the social issues affecting children, exposing the harsh realities of their lives and advocating for their rights and welfare. They challenged societal norms and called for reforms in child labor, education, and social support systems. The portrayal of child characters in Victorian literature served as a powerful means of raising awareness and promoting empathy for the plight of children, contributing to the eventual transformation of child welfare and the recognition of children's rights in subsequent years.

The Advent of Children's Literature

The 20th century marked the rise of children's literature as a distinct genre, with authors like Lewis Carroll, J.M. Barrie, and E. Nesbit crafting enchanting worlds and memorable child characters [5:313-328]. Carroll's "Alice's Adventures in Wonderland" celebrated the whimsical imagination of a young girl, while Barrie's "Peter Pan" explored the eternal essence of childhood and the conflict between growing up and staying young.

Psychological Complexity and Coming-of-Age

In modern and contemporary literature, child characters have gained psychological depth and complexity. Authors like J.D. Salinger, Harper Lee, and Mark Haddon have delved into the

inner worlds and struggles of child protagonists. "The Catcher in the Rye" presents Holden Caulfield as a troubled adolescent grappling with the transition to adulthood, while "To Kill a Mockingbird" explores the moral growth of Scout Finch in the face of racial prejudice.

Diverse Voices and Representation

As literature continues to evolve, there has been a growing emphasis on diverse voices and representation of child characters. Authors such as Jacqueline Wilson, Malorie Blackman, and Angie Thomas have introduced readers to child characters from diverse backgrounds, highlighting their unique experiences, challenges, and perspectives. These works contribute to a more inclusive and representative portrayal of childhood in literature.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the journey of child characters in English literature spans centuries, reflecting the ever-changing perspectives of society and the evolving understanding of childhood. From the idealized visions of innocence to the complex and multi-dimensional portrayals of modern literature, child characters have served as mirrors of societal values, sources of inspiration, and vehicles for exploring universal themes. By analyzing their transformation, thematic variations, and symbolic significance, we gain a deeper appreciation for the evolving roles and representations of children in literature across eight centuries of rich literary tradition.

The evolution of child characters in English literature reflects the changing societal, cultural, and psychological landscapes throughout history. From the innocence of early literature to the psychological complexity of modern works, child characters have served as powerful vehicles for exploring universal themes and societal issues. The portrayal of children has evolved to encompass a broader range of experiences, offering readers a deeper understanding of the complexities of childhood. As literature continues to evolve, it is certain that child characters will remain an integral part of storytelling, capturing the essence of innocence, growth, and the human experience.

References.

1. Bolt, D. (2008). The blindman in the classic: feminisms, ocularcentrism and Charlotte Brontë's Jane Eyre. *Textual Practice*, 22(2), 269-289.
2. Chandra, N. D. R. Representation of Children in Literature and Media: Aesthetics of Innocence and Violence. *Journal of Literature, Culture & Media Studies*, 18.
3. Kümmerling-Meibauer, B. (2008). Images of childhood in Romantic children's literature. *Romantic prose fiction*, 183-203.
4. Morey, A., & Nelson, C. (2012). The Secret Sharer: The Child in Neo-Victorian Fiction. *Neo-Victorian Studies*, 5(1), 1-13.
5. Nikolajeva, M. (2013). Children's Literature. In *The Routledge history of childhood in the western world* (pp. 313-328). Routledge.
6. Trim, M. (1998). A changing hero: the relevance of Bunyan's Pilgrim and The Pilgrim's Progress through three centuries of children's literature (Doctoral dissertation, Loughborough University).